

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL TYPES OF ANTONYMS

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Abstract:

The goal of the essay is to demonstrate the lexical-semantic nature of antonyms in Uzbek, taking into account their types with respect to their lexical meaning and structure. Additionally, the typology of Russian, English, and Uzbek antonyms is covered and illustrated with instances.

Key words: prefix, affix, suffix, derivative, compound antonyms, single-root and multi-root antonyms, proper-complex, paired, and compound antonyms are all included in the comparative-typological method

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Introduction

A ubiquitous phenomena known as Antonymy has been seen in a variety of languages and linguistic contexts. It is the primary expressive method of generating contrast, hence it is crucial to speech-thinking activities. We can say that antonymy is a somewhat paradoxical phenomenon because of the vague and multifaceted definition of the condition, the findings of this research, and the lexicographic processing resources provided in antonymy dictionaries. Comparative-typological analysis, which reveals the universal and specific in each of the compared languages in respect to a particular linguistic unit and category, is one way to delve deeply into the substance of a linguistic phenomena. We must look into the essence of antonyms in order to uncover their nature. However, there is disagreement even on this matter, particularly when it comes to determining what exactly makes up antonyms, or true opposites that exist solely in the "meaning of words" or elsewhere. The goal of antonym comparative analysis is to discover typological parallels and divergences across languages. Antonyms are one of the linguistic phenomena that has not received enough attention in both Türkology and Uzbek linguistics. The goal of researching antonyms in variously structured languages is to provide standards for the structural categorization of antonyms, research classification principles, and examine words that comprise antonymic pairings using derivational models. The Antonyms are words that are opposite in meaning and are in the same lexical paradigm. Antonymy refers to those areas of linguistics that attract the attention of researchers at each new stage in the development of this science and require revision and additional development each time. Antonymy must be considered in different aspects.

By their structure, antonyms are heterogeneous. Some linguists include in antonyms only words with opposite sounds that sound different: 'pure-toza' dirty -

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iflos'; joy-quvonch' - 'sadness - qayg'u', 'good-yaxshi' - 'bad-yomon. Other scientists include words with positive evaluative content in antonymic pairs, opposing words with negative evaluative content, and negation is expressed with a negative prefix - un, -less; compare: comfortable- uncomfortable, interesting uninteresting or by prefixing i: tasty - tasteless, useful-useless. They correspond to the antonymic pairs of Uzbek language with the suffixes - li and - siz and prefix -be: aqlli- aqlsiz, odobli- odobsiz; foydali-befoyda, mazali-bemaza . The classification of antonyms is given in different languages in different ways. This follows, apparently, from the peculiarities of the structural type of the studied language or from the chosen principles and criteria. Antonyms of the English language are structurally divided into simple, derivative, and compound. Simple antonyms include antonyms that do not have any prefixes or suffixes: totake 'olmoq' - togive 'bermoq', white 'oq' - black 'qora', day 'kun' - night 'tun', cold' sovuq' - hot' issiq '. Derivative antonyms include words that contain prefixes or suffixes, or both prefixes and suffixes: happy 'baxtli' - unhappy 'baxtsiz', attractive 'jozibali' - unattractive 'jozibasiz, xunuk', equality' tenglik' - inequality' tengsizlik ', correct 'to'g'ri'- incorrect 'noto'g'ri' . Compound antonyms are formed from two words: toswitchon 'yoqmoq' - toswitchoff 'o'chirmq, lowland 'pastlik' - highland 'balandlik', broad-minded 'dunyo qarashi keng' -narrow minded 'dunyo qarashi tor', northland 'shimoliy mamlakatlar' - southland 'janubiy mamlakatlar'. Based on the structural principle, M.I. Fomina and L.A. Novikov divide the antonyms into 1) multiroot, where the opposite is expressed in different words: early - late, life - death, north - south and single-root antonyms, the antonyms of which are transmitted either by means of mutually opposite prefixes attached to the same word , or by adding a prefix that gives the original word the opposite meaning: bring in - bring out, covered-uncovered. Such antonyms are called grammatical.

Sometimes, it develops as a result of conflation of two homographs which are not actually related. a) lease smth. (from smb.):b) lease smth. (out) (to smb.)Cambridge Dictionary (CED) defines these meanings as follows: a) to make a legal agreement by which money is paid in order to use land, a building, a vehicle, or a piece of equipment for an agreed period of time"; b) to use or allow someone else to use land, property, etc. for an agreed period of time in exchange for money"The verb to rent has two opposite meanings: a),„to pay money to live in a building that someone else owns“ b),„to allow someone to pay you money to live in your building“: In Uzbek language: kingadir qarz berish - kimdirdan qarz olish, choy olib borish -choy olib kelish. Antonyms-euphemisms express the opposite softer, they form antonyms with the prefix - не.Forexample.:красивый -безобразныйandкрасивый - некрасивый, добрый - злойandдобрый - недобрый.In English: attractive- unattractive, kind-unkind; In Uzbek language: chiroyli – chiroyli emas, yomon- yomon emas. From the above, about the antonyms of the English and Russian languages, and comparing them with similar works in Uzbek linguistics, it should be noted that the antonyms of the Uzbek language on the principle of "single-root / multi-root" have not been studied at all. It should be noted that in the Turkic languages there is no consensus regarding single-root antonyms, the problem of enantiosemy has not been considered in detail. In this direction, first of all, the works of linguists of Kyrgyz linguistics should be noted. Complex antonyms can be divided into the following groups: proper-complex antonyms, paired antonyms, compound antonyms. Properly complex antonyms are formed on the basis of an attributive, object or predicative

relationship. Their structural components are closely related. Two words enter into a close relationship, undergoing phonetic changes or losing some morphological indicators. In proper complex antonyms, one of the components may not be used in its literal sense, some suffixes may be omitted, or they may lose their independent meaning of individual components, for example: *erga tegmoq* (to marry)-*erdan ajralmoq* (to divorce). Paired antonyms are formed by establishing a syntactic connection between the words: *boshdan-aoyoqqacha* 'beginning and end', *kunu-tun* 'day and night', *ertayu -kech* 'morning and evening'. It should be noted that paired words in the Uzbek language play an important role in a complex system of derived words. There are quite a few of them in the language. For example, the spelling dictionary of the Uzbek language includes about two thousand such words. Compound antonyms consist of several constituent parts, in the role of which nouns, adjectives, adverbs can be. Antonymic relations include, first of all, compound verbs: *yugurib kelmoq* 'run' – *yugurib ketmoq* 'run away', *yoza boshlamoq* 'start to write' – *yozi bitirmoq* "end to write". Conclusion Thus, in the Turkic languages there is no consensus regarding single-root antonyms; the problem of enantiosemy has not been considered in detail either. If in the Russian language antonyms enantiosemes are considered as a kind of single-root antonyms, in the Uzbek language they represent a separate independent group. In the Uzbek language, euphemism-antonyms are not so distinguished. The structural classification of the antonyms of the Uzbek language differs significantly from the classification of the antonyms of the Russian and English languages: as in Uzbek language the main emphasis is on word production of antonymic pairs (root or derivative word), and in the Russian and English languages it is highlighted whether the antonyms are single-root words or only words, consisting of different roots. In Uzbek language, the phenomenon of enantiosemy is hardly observed: the Yondi 'light bulb burned out' - Yondi 'light bulb has lit up'. In fact, logically, enantiosemy leads to antonymic pairs. However, enantiosemic antonyms were not included in the structural classification of antonyms. When structurally classifying the antonyms of Uzbek language, one should pay attention to the euphemistic antonyms: *chiroyli- xunuk* and *chiroyli-chiroyli emas* 'beautiful - ugly'. When studying antonymic pairs, one must take into account their relationship with words, phrases, phraseological units, with polysemy, with synonymy, etc., and all these aspects can be reflected only in a complete dictionary of antonyms. For example, if the Germanic languages and the Russian language have such dictionaries that meet all the requirements, then in the Turkic languages it is necessary to develop new principles and structure for the presentation of antonymic pairs.

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